

The NEID Port Adapter being assembled for testing before installation onto the WIYN bent Cassegrain port. (Credit: NOIRLab/NSF/AURA/D. Li)

NEID at WIYN

Jayadev Rajagopal and Dan Li

NEID is a highly stabilized fiber-fed spectrometer for the WIYN 3.5m Telescope at Kitt Peak National Observatory (KPNO), a Program of NSF's NOIRLab. The name is derived from the word "to see" in the language of the Tohono O'odham Nation, who graciously allow the scientific use of Kitt Peak under an agreement with the US federal government. NEID is designed to enable unprecedented radial velocity (RV) precision (better than 50 cm/s in a single epoch), which is needed to detect Earth-like planets. NEID is funded through NN-EXPLORE, a joint NSF-NASA program to enable groundbreaking exoplanet research.

Commissioning of NEID began in mid-October 2019 with the installation of the NEID Port Adapter (developed at the University of Wisconsin-Madison), a compact fiber feed that would be permanently attached to the bent Cassegrain port on WIYN and provide crucial functions such as target acquisition, guiding with fast tip-tilt control, and atmospheric dispersion correction for NEID. About two weeks later, the NEID spectrometer arrived at Kitt Peak from Penn State University, where it was built and extensively tested.

After two months of hard work by the entire team, NEID saw first light in late December, shortly before the

235th AAS meeting. The target of the first-light observation was 51 Pegasi, the first Sun-like star known to host an exoplanet (<https://nationalastro.org/news/neid-exoplanet-instrument-sees-first-light/>).

The very compressed schedule to make NEID ready for regular science operations continues at full speed. An issue with the Port Adapter's precision guiding system (consisting of a high-speed EMCCD camera and a fast tip-tilt mirror) where the guiding loop, under some circumstances, had trouble holding the target to the required stability has been resolved, and on-sky tests are in progress to

The cover being lowered carefully to close the two-ton vacuum chamber of the NEID spectrometer after the post-shipping inspection conducted inside the cleanroom where NEID is located at WIYN. (Credit: NOIRLab/NSF/AURA/E. Hunting)

further confirm this. Other ongoing commissioning tasks for the Port Adapter include incorporating an automated target acquisition algorithm (crucial to reduce observation overheads) and the capability to detect (and correct for) telescope-focus errors on the fly.

Initial data taken at WIYN showed some contamination of the surface of NEID's CCD detector from water-ice. The issue persisted after a few attempts to remove the contamination (by purging the cryostat with nitrogen and thermal cycling of the CCD). A solution involving an additional getter (cold absorption surface) and further minimizing the circulation of molecules near the CCD surface was devised by the NEID team and reviewed and approved by an external committee. At the moment, these modifications have been completed, and the chamber is being brought back to high vacuum. Regular commissioning and shared-risk science will be scheduled at the earliest possible date.

NEID's state-of-the-art equipment for calibration being tested in the cleanroom. (Credit: NOIRLab/NSF/AURA/D. Li)

NEID articles in NOAO Newsletter issues:

June 2020: <https://www.noao.edu/noao/noaoneews/jun19/119news.pdf>

April 2018: <https://www.noao.edu/noao/noaoneews/apr18/117news.pdf>

October 2017: <https://www.noao.edu/noao/noaoneews/oct17/116news.pdf>